
A KEY STUDY OF SOME DISEASES IN SATARA DISTRICT (MS) : A GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS

Mr. Santosh Prakash Patil,

(Research student) Assistant Prof, BDC, Patan

Prof. C. U. Mane,

(Research Guide) Associate Prof. & Head BDC, Patan

INTRODUCTION

Any Disease come from food, destroy the functioning of Human body “Disease is a specific symptoms and problems of all body and particular part of body. After the origin of earth and environment, human existed on earth. From existence, food, shelter and water is the basic need of human has completed from the environment. Till human is completed need of food from environment, health of human is not only better but also strong. In fact, human is clever as well as social animal settled over the earth. From the beginning, human is searched new techniques and technology for better life. With time, life of human becomes restful but has involved the several problems is referred as disease and depict the functioning of human body In fact, diseases have originated dominantly and increased after the industrialization mainly in the developed countries. The industrialization has resulted high concentration of industries in the geographical area of country. Those industries have produced the all pollutions like air pollution, sound pollution, water pollution, soil pollution etc. Generally, human is used oxygen in the process of respiration from the air, drink the water from the natural sources of water, also, food is taken from environment. All those need and sources is vital to existence of any human. Any mixing as well as change of basic need source has effected on human health. And that mixing and change is begun from industrialization which spread with industrialization at all over the world. Besides, diseases have happened to the eatable food, uncertain food time and concentration on any one food. While life of human is become dynamic and happiness from the scientific development and industrialization, highly invites the seasonal and non-seasonal diseases in daily life. Work, lifestyle and poor condition is the few reasons to the uncertain food time happened from the any human. Also, availability of particular food, economical condition and high interest is the few reasons of concentration of any food happened from the any human. Lastly, Own human is responsible for any disease occurs in his body.

CONCEPT

A disease is internal problem of human body made weakness as well as destroys the mental balance of human body. As different sources, the word disease was firstly used in its literal sense early 17 century as meaning of "discomfort, inconvenience of human body. From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, “A **disease** is any condition which results in the disorder of a structure or function in a living organism that is not due to any external injury “According to World Health Organization, A failure of the adaptive mechanisms of an organism to counteract adequately, normally or appropriately to stimuli and stresses to which the organism is subjected, resulting in a disturbance in the function or structure of some part of the organism.

Webster defines disease as “A discomfort, a condition in which bodily health is seriously attacked, and impaired, which is a departure from a state of health. An alternation of human body interrupts the performance of vital functions.”The Oxford English dictionary defines disease as “A condition of the

body or some part or organ of body in which it's functions are disturbed "Also, defines disease as "A condition which confines life in its power, period or enjoyment. Disease is a departure from a state of health. It means dismissal of ease and a person becomes uncomfortable and unhappy.

1. AIDS

Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS) is a disease highly spreading all over the world in recent years. In 1981, this was clinically first seen in the United States. AIDS is infectious disease has flu like illness early and fever, large lymph, loss of weight later. It is long term disease mainly caused by Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV). Some scientists believe that, the first human who suffer HIV was a person in Africa. The HIV is the chief factor of AIDS disease which primarily spread by unprotected sex, sexual contact, hypodermic needles, important exposure to infected body fluids or tissues, contaminated blood transfusions and from mother to child during pregnancy, delivery, or breastfeeding. Acute infection, clinical latency and AIDS are the three main stages of HIV infection. In Acute infection, person faces and suffers fever, a rash, headache, tiredness, throat inflammation etc. In clinical latency, people experiences weight loss, fever, muscle pains and gastrointestinal problems. Lastly, weakness, sweats, chills, fevers, swollen lymph nodes, unintended weight loss etc. health problems faces person in AIDS. As Report of World Health Organization(WHO), November 2017, an approximately 20.9 million people were taking HIV treatment in mid-2017. In 2016, almost 8 out of 10 pregnant women living with HIV, or 1.1 million women. At the end of 2016, globally, 36.7 million people were living with HIV. Hence, WHO has admitted the AIDS remains one of the worlds most significant public health challenges, particularly in low and middle income people. But, as a result of recent advanced medicine, prevents onwards transmission of HIV. In Satara District, In 2000-2005, about 52795 patients have tested but among that about 2901 patients found positive and in 2006-2011, about 102340 patients have tested but among that about 4816 patients found positive.

TAHSIL WISE AIDS DISEASE PATIENTS IN SATARA DISTRICT

Sr. No.	Tahsil	2000-2005		2006-2011	
		Tested	Positive	Tested	Positive
1	Jaoli	00	00	8011	377
2	Karad	00	00	9265	436
3	Koregaon	21142	918	12581	592
4	Khandala	00	00	9244	435
5	Khatav	00	00	7671	361
6	Mahabaleshwar	00	00	8925	420
7	Man	00	00	7947	374
8	Patan	00	00	5758	271
9	Phaltan	17869	835	12453	586
10	Satara	13784	1148	12091	569
11	Wai	00	00	8394	395
Total		52795	2901	102340	4816

Source: Tahsils Health Division of Satara District

Above table shows the tahsil wise AIDS disease data of Satara district which categorized into tested and positive information. In 2000-2005, Nearly 52795 patients have tested but among that about 2901 patients found positive. The Highest numbers of 21142 patients have AIDS tested in Koregaon tahsil, out of that about 918 patients in registered positive. But, in case of positiveness of AIDS, highest numbers of 1148 patients have registered positive in Satara tahsil where tested only 13784 patients. Also, in Phaltan tahsil, about 17869 patients tested AIDS disease and among these 835 patients in registered positive. Besides, tahsils- Jaoli, Karad, Koregaon, Khandala, Khatav ,Mahabaleshwar, Man, Patan, Wai, etc. have not registered and identified any patient of AIDS disease. In 2006-2011, About 102340 patients have tested but among that about 4816 patients found positive. The Highest numbers of 12581 patients have AIDS tested in Koregaon tahsil, out of that about 592 patients in registered positive. While, above 10,000 patients tested AIDS disease in Satara and Phaltan tahsil. Besides, Jaoli, Karad, Khatav, Mahabaleshwar, Man, Patan, Wai etc. tahsil have recorded tested nearly 9000 patient of AIDS disease. In the category of positive, above 500 patient recorded positive in AIDS disease in Koregaon, Phaltan and Satara tahsil.

2. DIARRHEA

Diarrhea is a disease observing all over the world. During 1350-1400, the word “Diarrhea” used in Middle English as meaning flowing through. Generally, many people face the disease diarrhea during less or more than days in once or twice each year. It has the condition of at least three loose as well as liquid bowel movements every day. The geographical factor mainly climate and water is responsible factors for that disease.

Today, diarrhea is most general health problems of people, have weight loss, fever, bloating, thirst, abdominal cramps, stomach pain etc. signs and symptoms. As report of UNICEF, Diarrhoea is a primary killer of children, nearly 8 percent of all deaths among children below age 5 world in 2016.

Also, bacteria, viruses and parasitic organisms are the vital factors responsible for diarrhea. Contaminated food and water has key role in disease have spread bacteria and parasites in human body. Hence, the poverty is a good indicator of the rate of infectious diarrhea in a population. These disease is

commonly found in developing countries but, very minimum in developed countries. It stands on the third place of significance among the diseases of India.

In Satara district, In 2000-2005, Nearly 1023 patients have infected but among that about 307 patients found death cases. In 2006-2011, About 832 patients have Diarrhea infected but among that about 195 patients found death cases.

TAHSIL WISE DIARRHEA DISEASE PATIENTS IN SATARA DISTRICT

Sr. No.	Tahsils	Years			
		2000-2005		2006-2011	
		Infected	Death	Infected	Death
1	Jaoli	119	36	97	23
2	Karad	43	13	35	8
3	Koregaon	57	17	46	11
4	Khandala	64	19	52	12
5	Khatav	193	58	157	37
6	Mahabaleshwar	84	25	68	16
7	Man	248	75	202	47
8	Patan	50	15	41	10
9	Phaltan	76	23	62	14
10	Satara	41	12	33	8
11	Wai	48	14	39	9
Total		1023	307	832	195

Source: Various Tahsils of Health Division, Satara District

Above table shows the tahsil wise Diarrhea disease data of Satara district which categorized into infected and death information.

In 2000-2005, Nearly 1023 patients have infected but among that about 307 patients found death cases. The Highest numbers of 248 patients have Diarrhea infected in Man tahsil, out of that about 75 patients in registered death cases. While, Khatav and Jaoli tahsil have noted above 100 infected patients. Besides, less or minimum diarrhea infected patient found in Mahabaleswar, Phaltan, Khandala, etc. tahsils. About death cases, medium i.e. 20-30 patient death cases have recorded in the tahsils- Mahabaleshwar, Phaltan, Jaoli, etc. Very less death cases have registered in Karad, Koregaon, Khandala, Patan, Satara, Wai etc. tahsils.

In 2006-2011, About 832 patients have Diarrhea infected but among that about 195 patients found death cases. The Highest numbers of 202 patients in Man and 157 patients in Khatav have Diarrhea infected but, among that about 47 patients and 37 patients have registered in death cases in Man and Khatav tahsil respectively. Besides, in the category of death cases, above 10 patient recorded in tahsils- Jaoli, Mahabaleshwar, Phaltan, Khandala, Koregaon etc.

4. Jaundice

Jaundice is also significant disease, generally reaches in the several areas of world. The term “Jaundice” is originated from the French language word jaune, which means yellow. The sign and symptoms have

yellow colour in jaundice disease. Actually, it is not a disease, but relatively a visible symptom of an underlying disease process. It occupies most area in developing countries, due to quality of food and water. Due to large population in developing countries, in daily life, peoples have less quality food as well as polluted water. Therefore, jaundice disease is highly observed in developing and poor countries especially in slum areas.

In fact, jaundice disease is commonly related with itchiness effecting on skin and eyes. It is due to high bilirubin levels, eyes become white and skin become yellowish and greenish. It build up distress the liver when this disease often in human body. Itching of the skin, dark-colored urine, dark-colored urine, whites of the eyes, yellow discoloration of the skin, mucous membranes, light-colored stools etc. are signs and symptoms sees in that disease.

In Satara district, In 2000-2005, Nearly 360 patients have infected but among that just 1 patients found death cases. In 2006-2011, About 144 patients have Jaundice infected but among that just 1 patients found death cases.

TAHSIL WISE JAUNDICE DISEASE PATIENTS IN SATARA DISTRICT

Sr. No.	Tahsils	Years			
		2000-2005		2006-2011	
		Infected	Death	Infected	Death
1	Jaoli	43	0	17	0
2	Karad	20	0	8	0
3	Koregaon	28	0	11	0
4	Khandala	30	0	12	0
5	Khatav	44	0	18	0
6	Mahabaleshwar	39	0	16	0
7	Man	50	0	20	0
8	Patan	27	0	11	0
9	Phaltan	36	0	14	0
10	Satara	21	0	8	0
11	Wai	22	0	9	0
Total		360	1	144	1

Source: Various Tahsils Health Division, Satara District

Above table shows the tahsil wise Jaundice disease data of Satara district which categorized into infected and death information.

In 2000-2005, Nearly 360 patients have infected but among that just 1 patients found death cases. The Highest numbers of 50 patients have Jaundice infected in Man tahsil is followed by 44 patients in Khatav tahsil, 43 patients in Jaoli tahsil, 39 patients in Mahabaleshwar tahsil, 36 patients in Phaltan tahsil. While, less or minimum Jaundice infected patient found in Wai, Satara, Karad, etc. tahsils. But, anybody patient is not registered in death cases in any tahsils of Satara District.

In 2006-2011, About 144 patients have Jaundice infected but among that just 1 patients found death cases. The Highest numbers of 20 patients in Man is followed by 18 patients in Khatav tahsil, 17 patients in Jaoli tahsil, 16 patients in Mahabaleshwar tahsil, 14 patients in Phaltan tahsil. While, less or minimum

Jaundice infected patient found in Wai, Satara, Karad, etc. tahsils. But, no one patient is not registered in death cases in any tahsils of Satara District.

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